
Reading the Room: Seeing and Atmosphere in *Wuthering Heights*

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Abstract

In the very first chapter of *Wuthering Heights*, the reader is introduced to Lockwood and his excursion to Wuthering Heights is narrated in full detail. The reader realizes that Lockwood, in his naivety, has seriously misjudged his first visit and, contrary to Lockwood, finds the whole interaction with the residents of the Heights quite strange. The reader, essentially, interprets the situation differently than Lockwood. It is this very strangeness, that previous scholarship has alluded to but somehow failed to satisfactorily question and assess, that is analyzed in this paper. Comparing and combining Gernot Böhme's essay, "Atmosphere as the Fundamental Concept of a New Aesthetics" with James Elkins book, *The Object Stares Back: On the Nature of Seeing*, and finally applying the combination of the two theories to the first two chapters of *Wuthering Heights*, this paper answers the following question: why is the atmosphere of the initial scene of *Wuthering Heights* strange to the reader and not to Lockwood? The main claim of the paper is that the reciprocally affectual relationship that connects seeing and atmosphere causes the discrepancy in the respective gazes of the reader and Lockwood and makes reader-identification with Lockwood extremely short. Böhme comments on the atmosphere that exists between the object and the subject and Elkins theorizes about the active nature of seeing, and how there exists a connection between the object and the subject, a connection that is dependent on both the object and subject, rendering both sides equally active. The combination of the theories helps to assess the strangeness of the first two chapters of the novel. Both theories are based on reciprocity and it is this very aspect that is examined and then applied to *Wuthering Heights* in order to make sense of the pervading atmosphere in the initial scenes and its receptance.

Keywords

Brontë, atmosphere, seeing, Lockwood, reader

Emily Brontë's *Wuthering Heights* "is one of the most critiqued novels in the English language" (Bensoussan 2017). Among the topics of interest that this novel has generated, likening the real reader to Lockwood has been one of the most contested ones and, consequently, been undertaken in several scholarships (Woodring 301; Worth 317; Brick 81). Although some critics admit that the reader only temporarily identifies with the new tenant, some aspects of this temporariness still remain to be discussed. One of the aims of the present paper is to examine said temporariness by assessing why the events of the novel, specifically the scenes presented in chapters one and two, are read differently by the reader and Lockwood.

The novel begins with the reader being introduced to Lockwood, "through whose consciousness all the events of the plot are ostensibly filtered" (Worth 315). The reader, in contrast to Lockwood, interprets the situation differently and finds the visit rather strange. Krupat's claim that one thing that connects all readers of this novel is that they all find "it strange" (269) rings true here. It also dawns upon the reader that Lockwood has seriously misjudged the situation. It is this very strangeness that curiously seems to elude Lockwood while affecting the reader so forcefully, that I want to analyze in this paper. Associating said strangeness with the atmosphere of the text, the driving force behind this analysis is the question, why is the (initial) atmosphere of *Wuthering Heights* strange to the reader and not to Lockwood? The main claim of the paper is that the reciprocally affectual relationship that connects seeing and atmosphere causes the discrepancy in the respective gazes of the reader and Lockwood and makes reader-identification with Lockwood extremely short. For this, I will use Gernot Böhme's essay, "Atmosphere as the Fundamental Concept of a New Aesthetics" in combination with James Elkins' book *The Object Stares Back: On the Nature of Seeing*, examining how the reciprocity between the gaze and atmosphere affects the respective perceptions of the reader and Lockwood.

To that end, I will first expound upon the difference between the reader and Lockwood with respect to the first two chapters of the novel. Then, I will detail the main ideas in Gernot Böhme's and James Elkins' respective texts, comparing the two works to examine how the theories elucidated in them complement, enforce, and/or hinder each other. Böhme comments on the atmosphere that exists between the object and the subject and Elkins theorizes about the active nature of seeing, and how there exists a connection between the object and the subject, a connection that is dependent on both sides, rendering them equally active. The main idea is that that both theories are based on reciprocity and it is this very aspect that I mean to analyze and then apply to *Wuthering Heights* in order to make sense of the pervading atmosphere in the initial scenes and its receptance.

Difference between the Reader and Lockwood

Chapter one starts with Lockwood detailing his first visit to *Wuthering Heights* and his introduction to Heathcliff, whose "black eyes withdraw [...] suspiciously under their brows" (*WH* 19) and his hostility towards Lockwood is immediately palpable. Heathcliff's whole demeanor is extremely rude, as he invites Lockwood in through gritted teeth, his tone utterly insolent and uninviting. Lockwood also meets Joseph, who

grimaces at this unexpected visitor, adding to the hostility of the situation. The chapter continues with Lockwood describing the inside of the house and his encounter with the dogs. Their behavior resembles that of their master and, incidentally, Lockwood's behavior with them matches his conduct with Heathcliff, as he tries "to caress the canine mother" (22) and she, in return, "bare[s] her teeth" (22) at him and issues forth "a long, guttural snarl" (22). The dogs ultimately pounce on him and he is barely saved from them. The chapter ends with Lockwood deciding on another visit to the Heights, all the while admitting that Heathcliff did not seem so inclined.

Chapter two witnesses Lockwood enduring terrible weather to visit the Heights again. This time, even his naïve optimism is not able to misinterpret the atmosphere of the place, at least not for long. He is at first left knocking on the door with nobody letting him in. When finally let in by "a young man without coat" (WH 24), more uneasiness ensues. After some small talk, entirely devoid of hospitality, Heathcliff enters and his interaction with Lockwood assumes such a character that Lockwood "no longer fe[els] inclined to call him a capital fellow" (26).

During tea, Lockwood tries to lighten the mood, thinking that he is the cause of the pervading tension. Blundering through suppositions about Catherine, Hareton, and Heathcliff, he "beg[ins] to feel unmistakably out of place" (WH 28). Things go increasingly downhill from here onwards: nobody is willing to escort Lockwood home in the thick storm and he is accused of stealing a lantern. Heathcliff and Hareton ridicule him his ludicrous fate, until Zillah the housewife takes pity on him and he is "ushered" (31) to bed.

Even though Lockwood is a part of the story-world and the real reader obviously is not, the two resemble each other in the fact that they are both newcomers to the story and, as it is Lockwood's narration that reaches the reader, both essentially receive the same version of the events that transpire. This especially holds true for the first and second chapters. However, as I will elucidate upon shortly, this is the extent of the resemblance between the two and efforts to identify the reader with Lockwood fall short of the mark.

And yet, several critics have attempted this very task. Collins theorizes that "Lockwood [...] exhibits the reactions that may be expected from the ordinary reader" (1947; as qtd. in Krupat 272-273). Worth concurs by admitting to a similarity between the reader and Lockwood, albeit a "temporar[y]" (317) one. The same conclusion is present in Brick's analysis as well, when he claims that the "preconceptions" (81) presented by Lockwood "are progressively shattered, if not so much for Lockwood, then certainly for the reader who has been allied with him" (81; emphasis mine). Lockwood continues to give the inhabitants of the Heights the benefit of the doubt, and Brick posits that the reader goes along with his judgement, until they cannot anymore (83), finally "cast[ing] [Lockwood] aside" (83) in the third chapter of the novel. McCarthy takes the opposite view when he claims that, instead of the reader reflecting Lockwood's folly and misreading the room, it is "Lockwood [who] mirrors our incredulity and lack of ease"

(50).¹ For him, it is later at tea in chapter two that the reader “reject[s] the narrator” (54). However, as the following discussion will clarify, the reader finds the atmosphere of the novel strange and this perception stands in stark contrast to Lockwood’s from the very first scene onwards. Lockwood, who does not feel anything is amiss, goes about valiantly introducing himself to the inhabitants of the dwelling and, by association, introducing them to the readers. Thus, the reader “reject[s] the narrator” (54) much earlier than tea.

Even though the reader’s version of the tale, “the odd world of the Heights” is “mediated” (Chitham 98) “through the filter of [Lockwood’s] language” (Marsh 7), eyes, and understanding, they see that which Lockwood does not. At its core, this mediated reality of the events implies that Lockwood does, indeed, gather that something is strange, but he interprets the strangeness differently, he justifies it, so that his mind fails to grasp the real situation at hand. Bensoussan merits his “vapidness” to his being an “emotional cripple” (2017). Lockwood is, indeed, perceived as a “dullard” (Worth 315) by the reader, mainly because he has failed to read the room from the reader’s point of view.

It is only from the latter part of chapter two onwards that the reader and Lockwood are on the same page regarding the situation at hand and its strangeness. At the commencement of chapter two and Lockwood’s second visit, despite being barred entry into the Heights, Lockwood spouts optimism by describing the parlor as “cheerful” (*WH* 24). It is of import to note that his previous description of the room, with its floor-to-ceiling showcase of dishes, a variety of foods laid out in the open, and the presentation of “villainous old guns, and a couple of horse-pistols” (20), did nothing to arouse feelings of warmth and “cheerful[ness]” (24) in the reader. Furthermore, Lockwood wonders at the tension in the room and concludes that such unamiable countenances cannot be daily occurrences. At this point, it would have been logical for Lockwood to cut his visit short. For if he truly believed that the tension in the room and the “universal scowl [the inhabitants] wore” (26) were not commonplace to the inner workings of the Heights, and that he “had caused the cloud” (26), he should have removed himself from the situation and retreated to his abode at Thrushcross Grange. But, contrary to sensible judgement, he stays put and joins them for tea. It is then that he “beg[ins] to feel unmistakably out of place” (28). His misconceptions are still in place, however, despite having witnessed the strangeness of the residents and their attitudes, for he thinks them a “pleasant family circle” (28). It is only later, when the extent of his mistreatment at the hands of the residents of the Heights exceeds all limits of courteousness, does he grasp the true meaning the situation he is in.

Thus, even though he is treated horribly from the very beginning of his acquaintance with *Wuthering Heights* and its occupants, it is only later that Lockwood realizes that he has seriously misread the situation. “In his extreme naivete, he believes that he understands the characters and their actions on just a first impression” (Shunami 460). The reader, on the other hand, realizes something is amiss from the very beginning of the story. As Bricks articulates it,

¹ In due course, McCarthy goes on to refute reader-identification with Lockwood. However, the grounds for said refutation are not Lockwood’s naivety, but rather his failure to be “the norm of polite society” (50) that some scholars believe he embodies. Hence, while McCarthy’s supposition does eventually concur with those proposed in this paper, the reasons behind it do not.

Intrepidly, Lockwood rattles off one misinterpretation after another about the identity of the people in *Wuthering Heights* and their (he presumes) normal relations with each other, discovering progressively that the girl is not Mrs. Heathcliff, that she is not married to Hareton, and that Hareton is not Heathcliff's son. Finally he comes to a dim awareness, if not an admission, that he has stepped into a land and a dwelling which are thoroughly incomprehensible, where none of his mundane methods of perception will apply. (81)

Hence chapter two serves as an eye-opener for Lockwood's naivety, albeit gradually.

The reader, thus, issues forth a "clear refusal [...] to allow Lockwood to represent [them]" (Farrell 183) and Lockwood is—understandably so—regarded with a sense of scorn by the reader. Hence, reader-identification with Lockwood is impossible, for the very first paragraph of the novel illustrates just how misled Lockwood is, as he "ludicrously misreads the protagonists' personalities in terms of a sentimental superficiality" (Shunami 467). Despite critics vouching for reader-identification with Lockwood, such a resonance is highly dubious, even briefly, unless "temporarily" (Worth 317) is understood to mean the first few seconds into the story, and thus, the reader has no opportunity to form "preconceptions" (Brick 81) or to adopt Lockwood's. Subsequently, implying reader-identification with Lockwood also means, in the same breath, to impose Lockwood's naivety on the reader, making it doubly false to associate the reader with the first narrator of *Wuthering Heights*.

Contrary to the above-mentioned analysis, some scholars consider Lockwood's folly to be "irony" on his part (Woodring 301), his receptance of Heathcliff "genteelly sarcastic" (Galef 246), as he "finds Heathcliff disgustingly unsociable" (Woodring 301). However, this seems to be a misreading, for Lockwood's attitude towards Heathcliff only changes after multiple interactions with him and certainly not in the first moments of greeting where he considers Heathcliff "a capital fellow!" (*WH* 19). Had his behavior truly been ironic, he would not have misinterpreted Heathcliff's subsequent dealings with him and certainly would not have returned for a second visit. Therefore, Lockwood does not seem to be the "brittle ironist" (301) that Woodring claims he is.

For the real reader then, Lockwood is nothing but another reader (Farrell 183), who has been allowed to enter the "inner sanctum" (183) of the story but has not been given the privilege of commenting on it because of his very reader-like countenance (183). Farrell uses this as grounds to assert the performing nature of the implied reader of the text, who tries to go beyond "Lockwood's ineptitude" (183) and see through to glean the actual tale at hand (183-184). However, I opine that Lockwood's readerly nature can be utilized as grounds for the real reader, as well as the implied reader, to reject Lockwood's interpretation of events and instead, try to make sense of the incidents that take place on their own terms.² For the real reader surely cannot be duped by the narrative

² Farrell makes note of the performing nature of the real reader who tries to see past Lockwood's folly, but he does not elaborate on it further, nor does he associate it solely with Lockwood's naivety, instead blaming it on "the project of simultaneously associating and dissociating Lockwood and the reader, [that] is crucial to the narrative discourse of the novel" (184).

ability of a character who cannot even discern the most basic of human emotions, that of disregard and animosity for others.

Atmosphere and the Gaze: James Elkins' *The Object Stares Back: On the Nature of Seeing*

Elkins understands seeing as a concept that is enmeshed with various contexts of partialities and “passions” (11). The act is “irrational, inconsistent and undependable” (11) and is metamorphic not only towards the seer, but towards the seen as well (11-12), making it a reciprocal concept, for the observed is also the observer and vice versa (12). Elkins makes a note of the fact that he only erratically distinguishes between “‘vision’, [that is] the anatomical act of seeing” (19) and “‘sight’, [that is,] the wider senses of seeing, from suspicion to unconscious desires” (19). The reason he provides is that the two dimensions of the act of looking typically find themselves entangled within one another, so that it is difficult “to separate anatomy from history, manners, or psychology” (19).

Hence, seeing is never “just looking”, for all seeing occurs with a purpose (19-20). It is entangled in desires and ideas; it is always searching (22). In fact, eyes, like other sensory organs, “are specialized” (33) to “actively search” (33). For “there is no looking without thoughts of using, possessing, repossessing, owning, fixing, appropriating, keeping, remembering and commemorating, cherishing, borrowing, and stealing. [...] Those appetites don't just accompany looking: they are looking itself” (22). Seeing is never “objective” (33) and “‘objective’ descriptions are permeated, soaked, with our unspoken, unthought desires” (33). Thus, neutrality is a moot concept, as far as seeing is concerned, seeing simply cannot be neutral, for it has the potential to become violent, in the sense that it involves obtaining possession or being possessed in return, or even both simultaneously (29).

Seeing also has the ability to produce something previously nonexistent (30), for that which appeals to the eye is not limited to the eye only but reaches out its tentacles to encompass the mind and the therein lying prejudices, interests, and contexts (24-25). In fact, further contemplation on the subject leads to the obvious conclusion that “what *sees* is the mind, the person connected to the eye, but the eye itself is just tissue” (48; emphasis in original). In this respect as well, observing is highly subjective. Our eyes mold shapes in and around existing objects in accordance with our desires (30). “Sometimes the desire to possess what is seen is so intense that vision reaches outward and *creates* the object themselves” (29; emphasis in original). This “desire to possess” sustains “an urge to capture and domesticate” (31). “If the desire grows large enough, it can impel us to make what we want to see out of a whole cloth” (30). “An image is not a piece of data in an information system. It is a corrosive, something that has the potential to tunnel into me, to melt part of what I am and re-form it in another shape” (42). A lover, for example, sees an image of the beloved that eludes others (30). Should the love cease to exist, the image changes accordingly, although it still may elude others (30).

Additionally, seeing is even more complicated in the fact that it is also “inconstant seeing, partial seeing, poor seeing, and not seeing, [it] involves and entails blindness: seeing is also blindness” (95). “There are things we don't see, even when we are looking

straight at them” (12). No matter how hard one looks, one cannot capture the whole vision. Something always eludes seeing. This blindness occurs subconsciously for the most part. Elkins conjectures that it is the most uninteresting part of a scene that we tend to skip (95-96). To me, this sounds like another instance where the eye is seeing and one’s desires and hopes are pulling the strings. “Each act of vision mingles seeing with not seeing” (201) and this interplay, this “determinate trading of blindnesses and insights” (202) depends on one’s interests and desires.

Furthermore, “when it comes to seeing, objects and observers alter one another and meaning goes in both directions” (43), because the observed is also concurrently the observer and vice versa. And the same applies to the other end of this continuum as well: the object is many objects, for observation has changed its nature and keeps changing it every moment (43). “In the end, [looking] corrodes the object and observer until they are lost in the field of vision. I once was solid, and now I am dissolved: that is the voice of seeing” (45). One can, thus, talk about observers and the observed in the plural (43). “There is ultimately no such thing as an observer or an object, only a foggy ground between the two” (44). Hence, the object also looks and the reciprocal relationship between object and observer is continuous and never-ending, with the object-observer distinction hazy (44).

Atmosphere and the Gaze: Gernot Böhme’s “Atmosphere as the Fundamental Concept of a New Aesthetics”

Böhme starts with the general usage of the term “atmosphere” in aesthetical and political narratives, which concurs with describing something “indeterminate, difficult to express” (113), what Rita Felski (2015) would call “mood”. He further asserts that the general use of the word is much more exact, with atmosphere being used to describe “persons, spaces, and [...] nature” (113). However, it is still not exact enough, for atmosphere is a notion somewhere between “subject and object” (114). Böhme calls for a “new aesthetics” (114) based on the idea that human aspects or “states” (114), as he calls them, and the environment, are connected through atmosphere.

Böhme leans on Walter Benjamin’s and Hermann Schmitz’s concepts of aura and atmosphere respectively to develop his own theory of atmosphere. Walter Benjamin’s concept of aura derives from the physical world and defines artworks and their core (116-117) and one experiences it by “breathing” it in (117), by absorbing it in one’s body (117-118). For Benjamin, aura is a “spatial” (117) quality, at least for the initial definition.

Hermann Schmitz’s notion of atmosphere resembles Benjamin’s in that that it possesses a “spatial character” (118), yet goes on to neutralize the effects of things from which these atmospheres emanate (118). These atmospheres affect the perceiver and generate change in them (119). It is, thus, the atmosphere that makes the perceiver (120). Nevertheless, Schmitz’s concept is still lacking. Firstly, in the fact that that he subsumes aesthetics under the heading of formal art (119-120) and secondly, in atmosphere’s too great an independence, too great a distance from objects (120).

Böhme own suppositions include trying to extricate atmosphere from the “subjective-objective dichotomy (120). To this end, the subject must be thought of in terms of its surrounding “environment” (120). The same applies to the object, which has

hitherto retained its closed-borders policy, to set forth its existence and extend it to its surroundings (121). For the latter, Böhme comes up with the notion that things, instead of limiting their space by adhering to a fixed form, essentially radiate their form into the environment by giving the illusion of movement in the environment through their form and volume (121). He takes the example of a “blue cup” (121), whose “blueness [...] radiates out to the environment” (121) surrounding the cup, thereby “colouring” (121) said environment. “The blueness is a way of the cup being there, an articulation of its presence, the way or manner of its presence” (121). The “ways” (121) in which objects set their existence forth, “go[] forth from [it]sel[f]” (121) are termed “the ecstasies of the thing” (121).

This inclusion of the subject and the object in the environment serves to disintegrate the subject-object dichotomy, bringing Böhme full circle, in that that he is now able to further refine the concept of atmosphere, classifying it as an intermediary between the physical and the human world (114). “As opposed to Schmitz’s approach, atmospheres are thus conceived not as free floating but on the contrary as something that proceeds from and is created by things, persons, or their constellations” (122). “‘Scenes’ of a certain quality of feeling can be produced through the choice of objects, colours, sounds, etc.” (123); their “interaction” (124) generates “the character” (124) of a place. “Words” (124) can also produce “atmospheres” (124): “the particular quality of a story, whether read or heard, lies in the fact that it not only communicates to us that a certain atmosphere prevailed somewhere else but that it conjures up this atmosphere itself” (124).

Hence, the “concrete properties” (123) of a place or text “radiate” (123) a certain atmosphere out into the surroundings and “what is first and immediately perceived is neither sensations nor shapes or objects or their constellations [...], but atmospheres, against whose background the analytic regard distinguishes such things as objects, forms, colours, etc” (125). Thus, “the primary ‘object’ of perception is atmospheres” (125) and “perception is understood as the experience of the presence of persons, objects and environments” (116).

Böhme concludes that atmospheres are strung between subjects and objects, neither belonging to subjects nor to objects, but possessing subject and thing like qualities (122), existing forevermore on the invisible strands connecting subjects and objects. “Atmosphere is the common reality of the perceiver and perceived” (122) and what one perceives when looking at an object is essentially its atmosphere, rather than the physical form (125).

The Relationship between Seeing and Atmosphere

It is this very idea, that what one perceives when looking at an object is essentially its atmosphere (Böhme 125) that is of import when talking about the interchange between seeing and atmosphere. Elkins’ understanding of seeing renders looking a highly active and metamorphic process (11-12), convoluting the perceived or the looked upon in various ways (43-45), and the process is not unidirectional, so that it is not only the subject which looks, but also the object, thereby eliminating the subject-object dichotomy (43-45). “When it comes to seeing, objects and observers alter one another and meaning

goes in both directions" (43). Moreover, seeing is never neutral, for the eye reaches back to the mind which is, in turn, seeped in prejudices, preferences, contexts, and ideas (24-25). Hence, seeing is always subjective. Böhme theorizes that things radiate their form into the environment (121), that atmospheres are strung between subjects and objects, neither belonging to subjects not to objects, but possessing subject and thing like qualities (122), existing forevermore on the invisible strands connecting subjects and objects. One can observe that Elkins' conception of looking resembles Böhme's conception of atmosphere and what one perceives when looking at an object is essentially its atmosphere, rather than the physical form (125). Both eliminate the subject-object distinction, and both imagine there to be a connection between the two sides.

In developing his theory of a new aesthetics, Böhme conceived perception to be "the experience of the presence of persons, objects and environments" (116). In terms of the gaze, this 'experience' occurs through the eye and it's seeing, which leads to this "perception [...] of the presence of persons, objects and environments" (116). Thus, perception is automatically rooted in the preconceptions that are encapsulated in the mind and that are condensed into the act of seeing, into the light that is reflected off of the object and enters the eye. "Atmosphere is the common reality of the perceiver and perceived" (122), and the method used for said perception is that of the gaze. "There is ultimately no such thing as an observer or an object, only a foggy ground between the two" (Elkins 44). The "foggy ground" being the atmosphere that connects the two sides of vision, the "common reality of the perceiver and perceived" (Böhme 122). "In the end, [looking] corrodes the object and observer until they are lost in the field of vision. I once was solid, and now I am dissolved: that is the voice of seeing" (Elkins 45). "The primary 'object' of perception is atmospheres" (Böhme 125). In combining atmospheres and seeing, one can posit that "the primary 'object' of [seeing] "is atmospheres".

"An image is not a piece of data in an information system. It is a corrosive, something that has the potential to tunnel into me, to melt part of what I am and re-form it in another shape" (Elkins 42). Taken together with Böhme's description of atmosphere, the "tunnel[ing] into" occurs through the atmosphere that seeps out into the surroundings and is absorbed by the observer, changing the observer in the process. Of course, Elkins' use of the term change is more permanent than Böhme's. However, when a visual, a text, a quote, a picture stays with the observer even after it has long been removed from the observer's line of sight, is it not, in fact, the atmosphere of the object that stays behind?

Said change occurs on the other side of the spectrum as well. For seeing has the potential to change the object (Elkins 43). In coagulating seeing and atmosphere, we can conjecture that seeing changes the atmosphere of an object. The two theories blend well together, and a reciprocally affectual relationship between the gaze and atmosphere is evident. Furthermore, these ideas also revolutionize the element of power, for to say that both sides of the equation are equally involved in seeing and the generation of atmosphere is to automatically conclude that both hold power over the other and none is superior.

Lockwood and the Real Reader: Differences in Atmosphere and Seeing

With regards to the initial two chapters of *Wuthering Heights*, the atmosphere of the scenes “proceeds from and is created by [the] constellations” (Böhme 122) present in the scenes, namely the characters, their attitudes, and actions. Just like Böhme’s “blue cup” (121) emits its “blueness” out to its surroundings, it can be conjectured, that the scenes present in these two initial chapters also exude their particular quality of being strange out to their environment.³ This conjecture also automatically includes Lockwood’s naivety as a character in the novel, since his amiable reaction to the hostility further brings into light the strangeness of the scenes for the reader. Moreover, the strangeness of the text, just like “the blueness of the cup” (121), “is a way of the [text] being there, an articulation of its presence, the way or manner of its presence” (121). One may even call it’s the text’s identity, the way in which the text “goes forth from itself” (121): The “chained gate” (Miles 64), Heathcliff’s narrowed gaze, his clenched teeth, Joseph’s ill-manners, the dogs, and everything else that is odd in the scenes are an indication of the atmosphere of the text and the manner in which the text sets itself forth.

The strangeness is, therefore, an inherent quality of the text, made inherent by the characters present in the scenes and their attitudes. Just like “the choice of objects, colours, sounds, etc” (Böhme 123) produce “‘scenes’ of a certain quality of feeling” (123), the “interaction” (124) between words, gestures, expressions, and actions in *Wuthering Heights* “produce a certain quality of feeling” (123), that is strangeness. After all, “atmospheres” can also “be produced through words” (124). “The particular quality of a story, whether read or heard, lies in the fact that it not only communicates to us that a certain atmosphere prevailed somewhere else but that it conjures up this atmosphere itself” (124). Thus, the first two chapters of *Wuthering Heights* not only witness the prevalence of strangeness at the Heights and its surroundings, but also “conjure[] up this atmosphere” (124) of strangeness for us.

After this, perception of said atmosphere is just one short step away, for “what is first and immediately perceived is neither sensations nor shapes or objects or their constellations [...], but atmospheres, against whose background the analytic regard distinguishes such things as objects, forms, colours, etc.” (Böhme 125). Hence, it is this very strangeness, this very projection that is perceived, that is captured in the gaze of the reader and Lockwood. Shunami posits that Lockwood fails to understand

the significance of important occurrences which unfold before his eyes—at times because of Nelly's unreliable account and at times because of his tendencies toward melodramatic and distorted explanations of real events [so that] the reader is constantly involved in a difficult search after the true meaning of the events in *Wuthering Heights*. (467)

³ Krupat documents various scholars who sustain the notion of *Wuthering Heights* being “strange” (269) in one way or another. What said strangeness entails, however, although logical as a follow-up question, is not the matter at hand in this paper. I will only briefly comment that, firstly, critics tend to associate *Wuthering Heights* with the “sinister and [the] wild” (Miles 11), with “an atmosphere of storm and conflict” (10), so the strangeness can be at least in part attributed to visions of storms and turmoil. And secondly, there “are things we are vaguely aware of which create an unlimited but obscured environment around the story itself” (Marsh 10), things that, by eluding recognition, create an air of mystery, not only for Lockwood but through him, for the reader as well.

I would say that it is these “tendencies towards melodramatic and distorted explanations” which play a role in his nonunderstanding of the scenes that occur in chapters one and two, causing him to generate faulty interpretations for them. This, in turn, leads the reader to suspect that all is not as is being narrated and so leads the reader to “search after the true meaning of the events”. Thus, for the real reader, Lockwood’s misunderstanding is the first clue that something is amiss. “Lockwood’s inept comments set the tone of doubt and uneasy judgment which are such a part of the book” (McCarthy 52). Hence, the reader has to pause for a second right at the beginning of the narrative: as Heathcliff suspiciously narrows his eyes at Lockwood, the reader mirrors his actions. This weighs in with the particular constellation of the chapters and also aids in the generation of the prevailing atmosphere between the reader and the text, leading the reader to perceive the text differently than Lockwood. Therefore, the atmosphere being produced between the reader and the text is affected by Lockwood’s misinterpretation, the reader’s caution after realizing Lockwood’s error in judgement, and the constellations present in the text.

Here, of course, the obvious question that arises is, if the reader perceives the strangeness of the text because the text exudes it to its surroundings, should not Lockwood have perceived it as well, should it not have been just as noticeable to Lockwood as to the reader, even despite the lack of an element that enhances the oddity of the situation as Lockwood’s behavior does for the reader? The answer to this question is, that that said strangeness was, indeed, palpable to Lockwood. After all, it is Lockwood who narrates the goings-on for the reader. However, the way he registers this particular quality of the scenes is the pivotal point of this argument. According to Elkins, the mechanism behind the gaze is determined by the mind which, in turn, is determined by preconceptions and contexts (24-25). Lockwood’s and the reader’s eye are influenced by overtly distinct notions and preconceptions. Lockwood’s naivety, which is solely Lockwood’s and not shared by the reader, sees what the reader does not. Similarly, he is blind to those things that the reader sees. “There are things we don’t see, even when we are looking straight at them” (12), and “each act of vision mingles seeing with not seeing” (201) in a “determinate trading of blindnesses and insights” (202). Farrell posits that Lockwood “is so addicted to the social conventions of his class that he filters the whole story through his meager and mundane stereotypes” (181). His naivety, its fair to say, stems from these very “social conventions” that he finds so attractive, and thus, he sees differently than the reader. He “casts” (Miles 65) these visits “in the style of a polite visitor touring a country house [...] constructing himself as the genteel traveller, the delittante antiquarian” (65).

Therefore, even though both perceivers of the story do take notice of the strangeness of the ensuing situation, they interpret it differently, and in doing so, generate distinct conclusions. The reader proceeds to analyze the strangeness and become, subsequently, wary of the reliability of the narrative truthfulness of the upcoming events, while Lockwood, being “an unperceptive stranger, preoccupied by his own affairs” (Marsh 3), files the strangeness away as acceptable behavior, explaining it away in his own naïve manner, following “the misdirection of his [...] ideology” (Miles 66), thereby perceiving, reading the room differently than the reader. “A great deal of vision is unconscious: we are blind to certain things and blind to our blindness” (Elkins 13).

Lockwood does not realize that he has seen incorrectly, that he is blind to many aspects of his initial encounter with the Heights and its inhabitants until the latter part of chapter two when the blindness is converted into sight for him.

Thus, in interpreting differently than the reader, Lockwood's vision actively creates an atmosphere distinct than the atmosphere that the reader attributes to the work: Heathcliff's "jealous resolution" (WH 19) and "sullen[]" (19) demeanor were not signs of "reserve[]" (19), nor was Heathcliff himself a "gentleman-landlord" (Miles 66). Lockwood's "sentimental foolishness induces him to enter an imagined world of stormy melodrama which insulates him forever from genuine understanding of the characters" (Shunami 468). Such a reading is borne purely out of Lockwood's desire to make acquaintance with his landlord. His vision is responsible for taking in the strange atmosphere of the Heights and not deciphering it for its oddity and, instead justifying it as best as he can. In short, Lockwood desires to own the events that transpire and make him see a different *Wuthering Heights* than the reader. His justification of the strangeness is a tactic, albeit a subconscious one, to make the scenes his own, to become the master of them, "to capture and domesticate" (Elkins 31) their oddities. This is, perhaps, even more important if we consider that the rest of the story is essentially Nelly Dean's, Lockwood's voice only being used to render it explicit.

McCarthy deliberates in great detail about the contrast that Lockwood presents to *Wuthering Heights* and its inhabitants (53-54, 60). Especially the initial scenes where he is shown to be "out of his element" (53), serve to enhance the difference between Lockwood and the others. McCarthy claims "Brontë is not exposing the incivility of *Wuthering Heights* compared with the civility of Lockwood and his polite ways, but is preventing us from casting *Wuthering Heights* off by deflating Lockwood instead. For the contrast being made is one of depth, not of polite ways. It is Lockwood who is shown to be lacking, not only the others" (53-54). With this succinct explanation, McCarthy has laid the matter of *Wuthering Heights*' strangeness to rest: it is not the place and its people themselves that are odd, but Lockwood and his manners make them out to be so. Hence, as soon as Lockwood's farce is up, *Wuthering Heights* "is rendered less abnormal" (54) for the reader. This analysis, however, might have resonated better, had it not been for the fact that the novel's strangeness does not disappear after the first scenes, not does it lessen as time (in the story-world) goes by. The strangeness remains intact throughout the work, the reader cannot get rid of the uncanny notion that something is not right, and this view starts from the very beginning of the novel, the book "is marked for its strangeness instantly and even by readers who do not attend closely nor go to the critics for help" (Krupat 270), thereby contrasting the reader with Lockwood, for whom the environment only becomes peculiar in the course of his second visit to the Heights.

Considering atmosphere's work as an intermediary between the subject and object, atmosphere in this analysis exists between the story and Lockwood on the one hand, and between the story and the reader on the other. It is the data that goes back and forth between the two sides continuously and alters them, between Lockwood's naivety and the real reader's wariness, as well as the text's own constellations. Manipulated by Lockwood's "nullity" (Farrell 181, 183) "the enterprising reader [...] examin[es] over and over again the true significance of the characters' actions and the explanations for their

curious relationships” (Shunami 468). Hence, the reader’s gaze also affects the production of a certain atmosphere, and the teamwork of the two, the gaze and atmosphere, makes *Wuthering Heights*’ atmosphere a strange one for the reader. Lockwood’s gaze, in contrast, although receiving the same atmosphere, reshapes the context, so as to make sense of it on his terms. The same “nullity” affects Lockwood’s gaze as well and he sees what he wants to see, reimagining the irregularities he witnesses to make sense of them, to ensnare them in the prejudices of his mind.

Conclusion

The aim was to find an affectual reciprocity between seeing and atmosphere and this analysis has revealed that such a reciprocity can, indeed, be claimed. Moreover, this assessment also quite aptly provides an explanation for the temporary reader-identification with Lockwood. So, the reciprocally affectual relationship that connects seeing and atmosphere, causes the discrepancy in the respective gazes of the reader and Lockwood, causing both of them to read the room differently than each other.

Concurring with the claim that there prevails a strangeness in *Wuthering Heights* (Krupat 269), Krupat also analyzes the reasons behind this strangeness (270). He looks towards the “technique—the handling of the materials” (270) in the book in terms of Lockwood’s and Nelly’s narration for such an assessment. What he fails to consider is the disparity between Lockwood as the initial narrator, and the reader, and the discrepancies in their perception of the story. The current assessment shows the link between atmosphere of the novel and the gaze of the reader, real and fictional both, and in so doing, provides an explanation for the strangeness of the novel.

Chitham deliberates that “Chapters 1 and 3 are mainly concerned with establishing the ambience of *Wuthering Heights*, while Chapter 2 concerns a series of blunders and confusions suffered by Lockwood and felt too by the reader” (104). With respect to the chapters the paper has confined itself to, I agree that chapter one does, indeed, “establish[] the ambience of *Wuthering Heights*”, but I would also like to include chapter two here, for it is just as important in authenticating the “ambience”, the environment, the atmosphere of the Heights. After all, atmosphere “proceeds from and is created by [the] constellations” (Böhme 122) present in a situation, a place. Indeed, even Lockwood’s “series of blunders and confusions” contribute to establishing the atmosphere of the dwelling, and their being “felt [...] by the reader” only further verifies the notion of atmosphere and “ambience” in chapter two.

Watson observes, “never, probably, will an interpretation of *Wuthering Heights* be made which will satisfy all people for all time, for a masterpiece of art has a life of its own which changes, develops, and unfolds as the generations pass” (262). The interpretation that this paper offers might not resonate with all readers. Perhaps, some, like Lockwood, may misread the claims presented here. However, even disagreement would only testify to the resilience of atmosphere and its effects on the gaze and vice versa, for in misinterpreting, misreading, they will be aiding in generating atmospheres, atmospheres that can only exist in their particular interaction with the text and its qualities, thereby confirming the reciprocity between the gaze and atmosphere.

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